

Derivatives of Tellurium with Glycols

R. C. Mehrotra and S. N. Mathur

Reactions of tellurium isopropoxide with glycols (ethylene, 1,2- & 1,3-propylene, 1,3-, 2,3- & 1,4-butylene, pentamethylene, hexylene, and pinacol) have been studied. The reactions in the molar ratio of 1:1 afford tellurium di-isopropoxide monoglycollates, whereas in the molar ratio of 1:2, tellurium diglycollates are formed. The diglycollates, except those derived from butane-1,4-diol and pentamethylene glycol, are volatile under reduced pressure. The di-isopropoxide monoglycollates disproportionate under reduced pressure, yielding diglycollates and tellurium isopropoxide, except the pentamethylene glycol derivative which appears to undergo decomposition.

The preparation and properties of glycol derivatives of aluminium¹, boron², titanium,³ germanium⁴, and antimony⁵ have been studied recently in these laboratories. As glycol derivatives of tellurium does not appear to have been investigated, it has been considered worth while to extend these studies to tellurium also.

The reactions of tellurium isopropoxide with various glycols in different molar ratios have been carried out. In molar ratio of 1:1, tellurium di-isopropoxide monoglycollates are formed in all cases, which disproportionate to tellurium diglycollates, providing tellurium isopropoxide on volatilisation under reduced pressure, except the pentamethylene glycol derivative which decomposes under these conditions. In molar ratio of 1:2, tellurium diglycollates are formed which, with the exception of butane-1,4-diol and pentamethylene glycol derivatives, volatilise under reduced pressure.

The reactions taking place can be represented by the following general equations:

where $\text{R} \begin{array}{l} \text{OH} \\ \text{OH} \end{array}$ stands for glycolis, ethylene, 1,2- & 1,3-propylene, 1,3-, 2,3-, & 1,4-butylene, pentamethylene, hexylene, and pinacol).

1. Mehrotra and Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1962, **39**, 635.
2. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1032.
3. Puri, Ph. D. Thesis, University of Gorakhpur, 1962.
4. Mehrotra and Chandra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2804.
5. Mehrotra and Bhatnagar, *this Journal*, 1965, **42**, 327.

The diglycollate derivatives of ethylene, pentamethylene, and 1,4-butylene glycols are insoluble in benzene and those of 1,2- and 1,3-propylene, 1,3- and 2,3-butylene, glycols and pinacol are soluble in benzene. The hexylene diglycollate crystallises in benzene in cold. All the di-isopropoxide monoglycollates, except those of ethylene and pentamethylene glycols, are soluble in benzene.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable joints was used throughout the work and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. For fractionation, a column packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total-condensation variable take-off stillhead was used.

The reagents were dried in the usual manner described earlier⁶. Glycols were purified by distillation before use. Tellurium isopropoxide was prepared by sodium alkoxide method⁷.

Tellurium was estimated as tellurium dioxide by hydrolysing the compound with HCl (dil.) and using 20% aqueous solution of hexamine as the precipitating agent. The isopropanol in the azeotrope was estimated by an oxidimetric method⁸.

Reaction between Tellurium Isopropoxide and Ethylene Glycol

(a). *In Ratio 1:1*.—To tellurium isopropoxide (2.0 g.) in benzene was added glycol (0.34 g.). A white solid, which remained insoluble in refluxing benzene, separated in cold. The contents were refluxed under a column for 1 hr. and the binary azeotrope of alcohol and benzene appearing at 72° was slowly collected. Refluxing was continued till the distilling liquid did not show any tendency of lowering of the temperature below 80°. Excess of the solvent was distilled and on drying the contents under reduced pressure tellurium di-isopropoxide monoglycollate in the form of a white solid (1.63 g.) was obtained. It is insoluble in benzene. On sublimation it disproportionates to tellurium ethylenediglycollate (0.532 g.) at 145°/1.5 mm.

For unsublimed product: [Found: Te, 41.86. $\text{Te}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ requires Te, 41.73%]. *i*-PrOH in azeotrope found: 0.67g. Calc. 0.65g.

For sublimed product: [Found: Te, 50.85. $\text{Te}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_2$ requires Te, 50.51%].

It could be sublimed at 145°/1.5 mm (0.756 g.). [Found: Te, 51.6. $\text{Te}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_2$ requires Te, 50.51%]. *i*-PrOH in azeotrope found: 1.60g. Calc. 1.60g.

(b). *In Ratio 1:2*.—Tellurium ethylene diglycollate was obtained, when worked up as in (a). It could be sublimed at 145°/1.5 mm (0.756 g.). [Found: Te, 51.60. $\text{Te}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_2$ requires Te, 50.51%].

Similar reactions were carried out in the case of other glycols and the results are recorded in the following tables.

6. Mehrotra and Mathur, *this Journal*, 1964, **41**, 111.

7. Mehrotra and Mathur, *ibid.*, 1965, **42**, 1.

8. Bradley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.

TABLE I

Reactions of tellurium isopropoxide with glycols in the molar ratio of 1:1.

No.	Reactants.	Product and state of yield.	%Tellurium in products.		Alcohol in azeotrope (in g.)			
			Unvolatilised.	Volatilised.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	TI (2.12 g.) + propano-1,2-diol (0.36 g.)	TD monopropylene-G (1.75g.). A white, low-melting solid, soluble in benzene. Disproportionates to tellurium dipropylene-G (0.52g.) on distillation at 50°/0.5mm.	40.22	39.89	40.13	40.26	0.67	0.69
2.	TI (1.98 g.) + trimethyleneglycol (0.42 g.)	TD monotrimethylene-G (1.63 g.). A colorless viscous liquid, soluble in benzene. Disproportionates to tellurium ditrimethylene-G (0.35 g.) on distillation at 131°/1.5mm and giving out TI (0.13g.).	40.45	39.89	46.48	46.26	0.62	0.64
3.	TI (3.1g.) + butane-1,3-diol (0.77 g.)	TD monobutane-1,3-G (2.73g.). A colorless viscous liquid, soluble in benzene. Disproportionates to tellurium dibutane-1,2-G (0.72 g.) on distillation at 108°/0.5mm and giving out TI (0.18g.).	38.32	38.25	41.65	42.01	0.98	0.99
4.	TI (2.80 g.) + butane-2,3-diol (0.70 g.)	TD monobutane 2,3-G. (2.3 g.). A colorless viscous liquid, soluble in benzene Disproportionates to tellurium dibutane-2,3-G (0.68 g.) on distillation at 106°/0.5mm, providing TI (0.15g.).	38.44	38.25	42.01	42.01	0.88	1.0
5.	TI (1.75 g.) + butane-1,4-diol (0.44 g.)	TD monobutane -1,4-G (1.57 g.). Soluble in benzene. Disproportionates to tellurium dibutane-1,4-G (0.12g.) on sublimation at 110°/0.5mm.	38.24	39.89	41.82	42.01	0.55	0.57
6.	TI (2.05g.) + pentamethylene glycol (0.59g.)	TD monopentamethylene-G (1.85 g.). A white solid, insoluble in benzene, decomposes on distillation.	37.05	36.36	..	..	0.66	0.67
7.	TI (1.2 g.) + pinacol (0.39g.)	TD monopinacollate (1.14g.). A white solid, soluble in benzene. Disproportionates to tellurium dipinacollate (0.22g.) on sublimation at 110°/0.5 mm, providing TI (0.2g.).	35.73	35.26	35.23	35.45	0.39	0.39
8.	TI (2.07g.) + hexylene glycol (0.67g.)	TD monohexylene-G (1.98g.). A white solid, soluble in benzene. Disproportionates to tellurium dihexylene-G (0.85g.) and affording TI (0.15g.).	35.58	35.26	35.68	35.45	0.66	0.67

N. B. TI, TD, and G denote respectively tellurium isopropoxide, tellurium di-isopropoxide, and glycollate.

TABLE

Reaction of tellurium isopropoxide with glycols in the molar ratio of 1:2.

No.	Reactants.	Product and state of yield.	%Tellurium.		Alcohol in azeotrops (g.).	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	TI (2.57g.)+propane-1,2-diol (1.08 g.)	Te dipropylene-G. A white solid (1.93 g.), soluble in benzene, distilled at 80°/0.5mm (1.56 g.).	46.28	46.20	1.65	1.68
2.	TI (2.65 g.)+trimethylene glycol (1.11g.)	Te ditrimethylene-G. (2.0 g.). A colorless viscous liquid, soluble in benzene, distilled at 131°/1.5mm (1.35g.).	46.32	46.26	1.70	1.72
3.	TI (2.9 g.)+butane-1,3-diol (1.5 g.)	Te dibutane-1,3-G (2.38 g.). A colorless viscous liquid, soluble in benzene, distilled at 108°/0.5 mm (1.98g.).	41.78	42.01	1.85	1.87
4.	TI (2.69 g.)+butane-2,3-diol (1.3 g.)	Te dibutane-2,3-G. A colorless viscous liquid, soluble in benzene (2.2 g.), distilled at 106°/0.5 mm (1.84g.).	41.85	42.01	1.73	1.64
5.	TI (2.2 g.)+butane-1,4-diol (1.08 g.)	Te dibutane-1, 4-G. A colorless viscous liquid (1.77g.), insoluble in benzene, decomposed on distillation.	40.89	42.01	1.49	1.42
6.	TI (1.59 g.)+pentamethylene glycol(0.9 g.)	Te dipentamethylene-G (1.43 g.). A white solid, insoluble in benzene, decomposed on distillation.	38.25	38.45	0.99	1.03
7.	TI (2.09 g.)+hexylene glycol (1.35 g.)	Te dihexylene-G. A white solid (2.0g.), crystallising from benzene and subliming at 110°/1.5mm.	35.58	35.45	1.34	1.35
8.	TI (1.13 g.)+pinacol (0.73 g.)	Te dipinacollate (1.04g.). A white solid, soluble in benzene, sublimed at 110°/0.5mm (0.4g.)	35.23	35.45	0.73	0.74

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